

ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFECTIVENESS OF C3 FRACTION SPLITTING TECHNIQUES IMPLEMENTED IN SLOVNAFT REFINERY

Variny M.^{1,2}, Blahušiak M.¹, Mierka O.^{1,2}, Kováč N.³

¹Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovak republic

²GRUCON s.r.o., Nezábudková 24, 821 01 Bratislava, Slovak republic

³SLOVNAFT a.s., Vlčie hrdlo 1, 824 12 Bratislava, Slovak republic
miroslav.variny@stuba.sk

Abstract

Two different techniques are implemented in C3 fraction splitting in SLOVNAFT refinery regarding the means of reboiler duty provision and column head cooling. We analyzed the energy consumption of both techniques, pointing out all relevant energies and media that are consumed in these processes. Most of them have been found to be available at virtually zero marginal cost, the only one worth saving was the high pressure steam. Saving proposal aimed at replacing the condensing steam turbine, driving the heat pump applied in one of these techniques for a backpressure turbine has been found promising, however at present due to low steam price its pay back period is 4 to 6 years.

Introduction

C2 and C3 fraction splitting by rectification belong to energy intense processes, as the pairs ethane-ethylene and propane-propylene have quite similar boiling points on the one hand and a high purity ethylene and propylene products are required for polymer production on the other one. This leads to rectifying columns comprising over 100 stages and operating with very high reflux ratios¹. Heat demand for such processes can exceed 1 MWh per ton of C3 fraction and large specific heat duties have to be removed by cooling water or refrigeration in the overhead condenser at the same time. Therefore, great effort is undertaken to develop economically feasible C3 splitting technology based on membranes or hybrid systems^{1,2}.

Conventional C3 splitting process makes use of available low or middle temperature heat in the column reboiler and utilizes column condenser cooling by refrigeration³. Such designs are often seen in Ethylene plants where excess heat is available in quench water and the condenser cooling is integrated into propylene refrigeration circuit. FCC Units on the other hand utilize either low pressure steam in reboiler, or supply heat to the reboiler with the help of a heat pump^{4,5}; the latter design thereby uses a single heat exchanger as column reboiler and condenser at the same time.

The analysis presented in this paper deals with comparison of heat-pump and low temperature heat powered C3 splitting, both of them being installed and operated in SLOVNAFT refinery. Major energies and media consumed in these processes are assessed by means of their variable cost. This provides indices about which media consumption could be worth cutting down and leads to formulation of two saving proposals. One of them has potential for high pressure steam consumption decrease of several tons per hour and might be acceptable in terms of payback period if steam prices were sufficiently high.

Brief process description

C3 fraction from C3/C4 splitter in the FCC Unit is split into propane fraction, containing less than 10 % propylene and into >99.6 % propylene fraction. Heat for splitting is provided by a heat pump, compressing the overhead propylene vapor and discharging it into column reboiler. It is driven by a condensing steam turbine, utilizing part of the 3.5 MPa / 330 °C steam produced on-site. The column operates with reflux ratios around 15 which ensures stable propylene quality, suitable for polypropylene production. The heat pump turbine provides output up to 1.2 MW and the heat pump itself delivers heat input into the reboiler of around 10 to 12 MW, meaning that its COP is near 10 at full load. The typical steam consumption in the power turbine is around 7 t/h at full load. Thus considering purely the steam heat content as the process heat source, the corresponding COP lies around 2 to 2.5 [kW of steam consumed / kW of reboiler heat input]. Such process design enables the column to operate at somewhat lower pressures compared to conventional design, as the column head cooling to around 30 °C is performed by heat pump which would be nearly impossible by using cooling water.

The petrochemical C3 fraction splitter uses hot quench water with temperatures around 75 to 80 °C as heat source for column reboiler. Column head cooling is realized by overhead vapor cooling in a propylene evaporator; the produced propylene vapor is then lead to the last stage of propylene refrigeration cycle installed in the Steam Cracker. The column operated with reflux ratios between 10 and 15, depending on the feed rate, nearly always utilizing as much heat as possible from the quench water. The produced > 99.3 % propylene quality is suitable for polymerization process as this is equipped with further purification steps. Heat consumed in the splitter reboiler amounts to around 14 to 17 MW and is considered as for free, since the always existing excess heat in quench water that it not utilized here or in other applications, is to be got rid of in cooling water coolers. Schematic depiction of both C3 splitting processes can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic depiction of heat pump powered (A) and quench water powered (B) C3 splitting process.

Variable feed processing costs identification

Taken generally, following media are consumed on-site in C3 fraction splitting process: water steam, quench water, cooling water, electricity (for feed, reflux and products pumping) and mechanical energy (for driving the propylene refrigeration cycle). However, the costs associated with each of them have to be analyzed in order to define the variable and fix part. Following statements can be made pertaining to individual media:

- Water steam has its defined internal price that more or less copies the fuel price consumed in the Combined Heat and Power Unit (CHP) to produce water steam. However its consumption in the C3 fraction splitting varies only in a narrow range that is given by needs for certain minimal vapor and reflux flows in the column as well as by the power turbine steam consumption characteristics.
- Quench water can be considered for free and the costs associated with its pumping are fix to the most part. Its amount produced is given by production process and its heat content has to be given away either usefully (limited possibility) or in cooling water coolers.
- Cooling water is provided by a circulation centre. Only a part of its internal costs can be attributed to variable costs – small to moderate variations in cooling water flow rate and/or the temperature difference between the delivered cold water and received warmed up water do not lead to costs change, whereas big ones can. Costs change usually is associated with the variable number of circulation pumps in operation (realized stepwise) and to some extent also to number of cooling towers operated (also realized stepwise).
- Electricity for pump driving is negligible compared to other media consumption in the C3 fraction splitting process.
- The cost of mechanical energy consumed for propylene refrigeration cycle driving normally would comprise a decent variable part. However the propylene compressor installed on site is somewhat oversized for current cold needs, especially its last stage, leading to a constant flow of propylene vapor compressed in this stage independently on Steam Cracker feed rate due to always active antisurge protection. Due to this fact the variable part of mechanical energy consumed in the propylene compressor, related to C3 fraction splitting is zero; at least for non significant changes.

High pressure water steam in detail

The refinery imports high-, medium- and low-pressure steam from an Combined Heat and Power Unit (CHP) located within the refinery area that thus serves as marginal steam source. As reported elsewhere⁶, see also Figure 2 the mass flow of high pressure steam imported from the CHP dropped dramatically in the past and a new steam pipeline had to be built that exports decent amounts of high-pressure steam back to the CHP, where it replaces part of internal steam consumption, stabilizing the operation of the high pressure steam network in the refinery. On some occasions the refinery even acts as net high pressure steam exporter at present. Thereby any substantial high pressure steam saving it not very welcome and the saved steam would likely to be throttled down to middle pressure level, replacing part of the middle pressure steam import from the CHP.

Figure 2. High pressure steam network in SLOVNAFT refinery – typical operation with mass flows of steam in t/h and its flow direction indicated. C = consumer, S = source.

Saving proposals description

The above media costs analysis enabled us to gain clearer look on the process economics and led us further to formulation of two saving possibilities in the process:

1. Transport as much of the C3 fraction from the heat-pump driven splitting in the FCC Unit to the Steam Cracker, where it would consume zero-cost hot quench water. This would lead to some saving of the high pressure steam in the heat pump power turbine. After further inspection following issues have been detected that prevented this idea to be subject to detailed analysis:
 - Steam Cracker C3 splitter runs and is supposed to run on high capacity, leaving little space free for further feed increase. Splitter capacity increase has been considered in the past but is has been set aside as too costly;
 - The FCC-Steam Cracker interconnecting C3 fraction pipeline capacity is unsatisfactory;
 - The side product – propane – is obtained in higher purity in the FCC Unit splitter than in the Steam Cracker one, due to long-term problems with oligomers separation from propane that are formed in the methylacetylene-propadiene hydrogenation reactor that precedes C3 splitting in the Steam Cracker. C3 fraction from FCC splitting in the Steam Cracker splitter would thus lead to lower quality propane product.
2. Replacement of heat pump condensing steam turbine for a new one, of backpressure design. Such turbine would consume larger amount of high pressure steam that would lead to high pressure steam

network operation stabilization, but would produce middle pressure steam that would replace part of that imported from the CHP. As a side effect, the steam turbine condenser would be removed, yielding circulation cooling water consumption decrease of several hundreds m³/h. This might be sufficient to decrease the number of circulation pumps in operation in the circulation centre, leading to some electric energy saving. On the other hand, electric energy is cogenerated on extraction-condensing and extraction-backpressure steam turbines in the CHP. Increase of high pressure steam network from the CHP with simultaneous middle pressure steam export drop that result from this idea, lead to a decrease in power production that has to be compensated by increased purchase from the outer grid. It must be noted though that the price of electric energy produced in the CHP is not the same as that bought from outer grid. According to Slovak legislation [citacia], the in-house produced and immediately consumed electric energy is being charged with fees almost as high as that produced centrally in power plant and transported and distributed across country. Thus the value of electricity from the CHP is nowadays around 60 % of that bought from outer grid.

As such option appeared viable, it has been further investigated. This allowed for investment cost estimation that would amount to cca 1.5 mil. Euro. It includes following main parts:

- New backpressure steam turbine rated at 1.4 MW that according to our preliminary calculations would consume up to 27 t/h of high pressure steam and produce the middle pressure one;
- High pressure steam pipeline to the new turbine increase;
- Middle pressure steam pipeline construction and its connection to the existing network on site.

Results and discussion

As a result of the idea introduced above, the situation regarding high pressure and middle pressure steam import from the CHP changes as well as that regarding the electric energy cogenerated in the CHP. Following major factors were considered:

- High pressure steam import from CHP increases by 20 t/h on average;
- Middle pressure steam import from CHP decreases by 27 t/h on average;
- As a result the amount of cogenerated electric energy in the CHP lowers by 1.8 MW on average.

Following items were excluded from pay back period calculation, as they cannot be quantified exactly:

- Steam turbine condenser will no longer be needed, leading to cooling water consumption drop by 400 to 600 m³/h. Such large change could be sufficient to allow for decreasing the number of circulation pumps in operation in the corresponding cooling water circulation centre. Simultaneously additional small benefit will be realized by decreased cooling tower load, potentially leading to total power consumption decrease by up to 100 kW here.
- High pressure steam import from CHP increase might allow for further high pressure steam balance changes in the refinery that are restricted by currently very low high pressure steam import from the CHP. Especially in summer months the source S2 (see Scheme 2) could increase its high pressure steam export by up to 12 t/h and increase its low pressure steam import simultaneously, leading to power production increase in the CHP that would partly compensate for the anticipated drop of 1.8 MW.

The obtained simple pay back period calculation results are shown in Figure 3 that represents a parametric study regarding the steam and electricity price. The pay back period could be even shorter than two years with high pressure steam prices above 30 €/t and electricity price around or below 50 €/MWh. Such situation has been encountered in the recent past and lasted for over 2 years, however the current steam prices are less than half of it while the electricity price decreased only slightly. Under such circumstances the simple pay back period reaches 4 to 6 years. Obviously it could be shortened somewhat if the supplementary items regarding the possible electricity consumption in the circulation centre and the electricity production increase possibility due to further steam balance changes are taken into account.

We can thus conclude that under current steam and price relations the economic attractiveness of the presented idea is only mediocre and its implementation is uncertain.

Figure 3. Parametric analysis of simple pay back period depending on steam and electricity price.

Conclusions

By analyzing availability and cost of individual media consumed in two different C3 fraction splitting processes in SLOVNAFT refinery it has been found out that the only one medium worth the effort of saving is high pressure water steam. Other media and energies consumed here have virtually zero marginal cost. Based on this approach we presented and discussed two steam saving proposals with the first one appearing infeasible after deeper analysis. The second one would change balances of high and middle pressure steam in the refinery, negatively affecting both the electric energy production in the CHP unit but leading to steam production decrease in the CHP unit and other beneficial side effects. Considering the two years ago steam price the idea would exhibit an extremely favorable pay back period; with actual steam prices however its application is questionable. Further discussions and analyses are required to formulate a definitive conclusion about its economic feasibility and following realization.

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